

DETERMINATION AND EVALUATE THE ATTITUDE OF THE POPULATION TO WASTE TRUSHES

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Abstract. *The research was carried out in the form of a questionnaire, for five days, using the "Telegram" messenger. According to the results of the survey, 576 people read the questionnaires, but more than 199 people (35 %) actively answered the questions. 65 % (377 people) read the questions but they did not be active.*

Key words: *Trash, household waste, ecological culture, ecological activity, ecological responsibility, ecological ethics.*

1. Introduction

The daily increase in the number of people leads to a sharp increase in the amount of waste released from their household life. Types of household waste are also diverse, for example, up to 30% of waste is generated in the process of food production [1, 2]. In recent years, the increase in the amount of household waste affects the number and quality of natural resources, as well as global climate changes [3]. The percentage of recycling of household waste has different indicators on a global scale, and it is a very small percentage in general. In most of the poor countries, more than 90% of household waste is burned or thrown away without treatment [4].

In many cities, special places for household waste have been installed in public places, and these large containers help to prevent environmental pollution and separate waste into classification. But in most developed and developing countries, especially in our country, the number of such places installed along the city streets is much less compared to the population, which in turn seriously affects the environment with household waste and waste dishes lead to pollution.

Through a simple research (questionnaire) carried out below, the ecological attitude of the population of our country to waste places was checked and evaluated. The results of the research are very interesting and the answers to each question of the survey showed different indicators.

2. Method

The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for one week, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 576 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 35 % (199 people) answered the questions. 65 % (377 people) of those who read the questionnaire did not answer the questionnaire questions.

Figure 1. Active (35 %) and inactive (65 %)

3. Results

Answers to survey questions were also put into diagrams and analyzed. «Do you think there are enough special waste places (boxes) in the areas where you live and work?» and 201 people answered the first question, and the results were represented by the following diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

The second question of the survey, that is, "Do you dispose of waste in special waste boxes (dishes)?" and 201 people answered the question and the answers can be found in the diagram below (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The third question of the survey, that is, "Are you forced to throw waste into the environment in areas where there are no waste places or trash boxes?" and 193 people answered the question and the results of the analysis are represented by diagram (Figure 4).Figure 4.

The fourth question of the anonymous questionnaire, that is, "If a large number of garbage cans and trash dishes are installed, will the amount of waste on our streets in the city decrease?" and 197 people answered the question, and these answers are represented by diagram (Figure 5).

Figure 5.

The fifth question of the anonymous questionnaire, "If someone next to you is near a trash box (dish) and throws garbage around, do you encourage him not to do so?" and 203 people answered the question, and the results are illustrated by diagram (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

According to the first question of the questionnaire, the majority (69%) of the population believes that there are not enough garbage containers on the streets of our cities. According to the second question of the questionnaire, 79% of the population stated that they throw household waste into waste containers. 52% of people said that they would be forced to throw away in the absence of waste containers. In response to the fourth question of the questionnaire, 88% of people said that the environment would be cleaner if more garbage (waste) disposals were installed. 74% of the respondents who took part in the survey said that they have a negative attitude towards people who throw waste into the environment while the trail is a special place.

References

- [1] S.A.Tashpulatova., A.D. Khodiyeva. Studying the behavior of using from reusable containers of population of Uzbekistan. International Scientific and Practical Conference «Innovative development in the global science». Boston, USA. August, 2022.
- [2] Michal Misiak, Daniel Kruger, Jessica Sloan-Kruger, Piotr Sorokowski. Moral judgments of food wasting predict food wasting behavior. British Food Journal. DOI: 10.1108/BFJ-07-2019-0576.
- [3] Sintana Eugenia Vergara. Transforming trash: reuse as a waste management and climate change mitigation strategy. Dissertation. University of California, Berkeley. 2011.
- [4] The World Bank. What a Waste: An Updated Look into the Future of Solid Waste Management. September 20, 2018.